

Notes

Aluminon as an indicator for EDTA Titration of Cupric Ions

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ALUMINON (tri-ammonium aurine tricarboxylate) has been used as an indicator for EDTA titration of cupric ions. Titrations can be accurately carried out in the pH range 2.0-3.0.

The effect of variables such as concentrations, pH, temperature and foreign ions have been investigated.

Experimental

Copper sulphate solution: A stock solution of copper sulphate (0.1M) was prepared by dissolving 24.95 g copper sulphate in distilled water and making upto 1 liter.

EDTA solution: A stock solution of 0.01M Na-salt of EDTA was prepared by dissolving 3.723 g of EDTA in 1 liter of distilled water.

Indicator solution: 1.0% solution was prepared from pure sample of the reagent by dissolving the requisite amount in distilled water.

Metal solutions: To study the interference of various foreign ions in the estimation of Cu^{2+} with EDTA, the corresponding analytical quality of salts were taken and their 0.2M solutions prepared in distilled water.

Aluminon gives a pink colour with cupric ions. There is a sharp colour change on titration with EDTA from pink to light green as the end point approaches.

Effect of pH: When an aliquot of Cu^{2+} is titrated with EDTA, copper can be estimated accurately in the pH range 2.0-3.0 with the help of the indicators investigated.

Effect of Indicator concentration: Titrations were carried out with different concentrations of the indicator. It was found that an addition of 2 drops of 1.0% solution of the indicator gave satisfactory results.

Effect of Temperature: The titration could be satisfactorily carried out in the temperature range 10°-60°.

Effect of Foreign Ions: To investigate the effect of foreign ions, titrations of synthetic solutions were

carried out at pH 2.0 maintaining the pH by acetate-HCl buffer. Preliminary investigations indicated that PO_4^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} , S^{2-} , $\text{Fr}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, CNS^- , CrO_4^{2-} , Fe^{3+} , Ni^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Al^{3+} interfere seriously. It was observed that at 1.3 mg concentration of copper, 10 times excess of Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Cl^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} could be tolerated.

Suggested procedure: Take a 5.0 ml aliquot of solution containing cupric ions, adjust pH 2.0-3.0 using acetate-HCl buffer of pH 2.0, add 2 drops of 1.0% solution of indicator and titrate against 0.01M solution of EDTA with vigorous stirring to light green colour.

Standard Deviation: Five, 5.0 ml aliquots of 0.01M copper sulphate were analysed according to the suggested procedure. The standard deviation was 1.0%.

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Spectral Studies in Oxouranium(V) Compounds

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COORDINATION complexes of U(V) with nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands have been characterised¹⁻⁴. The complex, $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})_2\text{UOCl}_5$ has been shown to be an equimolar mixture of UCl_5^{2-} and $\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_4^{2-}$ complexes⁵. The oxochloro complexes of U(V) of the formulae, M_2UOCl_5 [$\text{M} = (\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_4\text{As}^6$, Cs^7 , $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^{8-9}$], $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}]_2\text{UOCl}_5$, phthalazine⁷, $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}]_2\text{UOCl}_5$ bis (1,10-phenanthroline)⁷ and $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})_2\text{UOCl}_5 \cdot 2.5\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NHCl}^6$ have been synthesised and characterised by spectral measurements. In the present paper the oxochloro complexes of U(V) of the type, $(\text{BH})_2\text{UOCl}_5$ (B = pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, α -picoline and β -picoline) have been isolated from UCl_5 solution in SOCl_2 and characterised by IR, reflectance and ESR spectra.

Experimental

UCl_5 was prepared by refluxing UO_3 or UO_2Cl_2 with SOCl_2 .¹⁻³ Pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, α -picoline and β -picoline (BDH AnalyR) were purified as already reported². Compounds of U(V) are very